

THE DETERMINANTS OF NON-USERS' INTENTION TO USE COMMERCIAL BIOPESTICIDES PRODUCTS: INSIGHTS FROM AN EXTENDED UTAUT2 IN THE CONTEXT OF INDONESIA

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Abstract

This study focuses on understanding the determinants of non-users' intention to use commercial biopesticide products among rice farmers in Indonesia. Despite biopesticides being recognized as an environmentally friendly alternative to synthetic pesticides, their adoption rate remains low. To close this research gap, an extended Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology 2 (UTAUT2) is used as the theoretical framework. The extended UTAUT2 incorporates various variables namely performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, facilitating conditions, price value, and perceived need. The study was conducted in Bogor Regency, West Java Province, Indonesia with the participation of 400 non-user respondents, who were selected through purposive sampling method. Data were gathered through a structured questionnaire. To analyze the data, this study employed a structural equation modeling (SEM) technique using Lineal Structural Relationship (LISREL) software version 8.72. The findings highlight that the determinants of non-users' intention to use biopesticides are effort expectancy, social influence, facilitating conditions, price value, and perceived need. However, the relationship between performance expectancy and behavioral intention is not statistically significant. Additionally, the study reveals that the extended UTAUT2 framework enhances predictive power by 75%, surpassing the original UTAUT2 model's 74%.

Keywords: Non-Users, Intention, Rice Farmers, UTAUT2.

1. INTRODUCTION

The utilization of synthetic pesticides frequently results in a range of health problems for farmers, including symptoms like dizziness, nausea, loss of consciousness, and other symptoms (Istriningsih et al., 2022). Considering these issues, biopesticides have arisen as a promising alternative to synthetic pesticides, given their eco-friendly attributes and diminished adverse effects. Nevertheless, biopesticides application by Indonesian rice farmers is still relatively low (Astuti et al., 2013; Izdihar, 2012; Kusnaya, 2014; Prabayanti, 2010). In order to encourage the sustainable adoption of biopesticides into rice farming techniques, it is essential to understand the determinants of farmers' intentions to use them. Previous studies have mostly focused on studying the biopesticides adoption among existing users, neglecting the perspectives of non-users. As a result, this study aims to close the research gap by empirically examining the determinants of rice farmers' intention to use biopesticides in the Indonesian context. This study recognizes that each nation has distinctive socioeconomic, cultural, and institutional aspects that affect farmers' decision-making processes. The theoretical underpinning for achieving the objectives of the study was an extended Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology 2 (UTAUT2).

UTAUT2 is a well-known theory that describes technology acceptance and usage behaviors. UTAUT2 has been considerably applied as a comprehensive framework in various contexts for understanding technology acceptance and usage, however, its application to biopesticides adoption among non-users, specifically in the Indonesian agricultural context, remains underexplored. This study closes this gap to serve empirical evidence by investigating the applicability and relevance of an extended UTAUT2 to identify the determinants non-users' intention to use biopesticides in rice farming in Indonesia. By filling the research gap, this study will significantly advance the body of knowledge. It will provide insightful information regarding the determinants of non-users' intention to use biopesticides among Indonesian rice farmers. Additionally, stakeholders involved in agricultural activities will benefit from this study. Policymakers can benefit the study's findings to design effective strategies to overcome barriers and provide support systems that enhance the adoption of biopesticides. Agricultural extension officers can utilize the study's findings to tailor their educational and training programs that can contribute to increased awareness, knowledge, and positive attitudes towards biopesticides among farmers, thereby facilitating their adoption. Biopesticide manufacturers can benefit from the study's insights by aligning their marketing strategies and product offerings with the identified drivers of intention, as a result, they can effectively communicate the value proposition of biopesticides and address potential barriers or misconceptions that farmers may have.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

UTAUT2 was built upon the original UTAUT (Venkatesh et al., 2003), to investigate the technology acceptance and behaviors related to its usage in a consumer context. UTAUT2 takes into account a number of important variables, namely (1) performance expectancy, (2) effort expectancy, (3) social influence, (4) facilitating conditions, (5) hedonic motivation, (6) price value, and (7) habit, which collectively affect the intention to use a certain technology (Venkatesh et al., 2012) (Figure 1). The use of UTAUT2 for research in a variety of scenarios has led to its development as one of the key frameworks for gauging acceptability of new technologies (Aggarwal et al., 2019; Septiani et al., 2021). UTAUT2 will be used in this study as the primary theoretical foundation for developing the conceptual framework because it has been demonstrated to be a reliable framework with superior predictive power to other technological acceptance models, which was able to explain up to 74% of intention variance (Venkatesh et al., 2012). This is a significant increase over what UTAUT can explain (70%) and the other technology acceptance models (17-53%) (Venkatesh et al., 2003). The conceptual framework will take into account five independent UTAUT2 variables namely (1) performance expectancy, (2) effort expectancy, (3) social influence, (4) facilitating condition, and (5) price value.

To further comprehend the phenomenon of technology use, UTAUT2 as the primary theoretical underpinning of this study, can be expanded with variables pertinent to the context of the study (extended UTAUT2) (Venkatesh et al., 2012). Drawing from the review of previous studies, this study will implement an extended UTAUT2 model by involving an additional variable that is potentially significant to the intention to use commercial biopesticide products, namely the perceived need variable (Fen & Sabaruddin, 2008; Mukred et al., 2020). In the context of this

study, non-users were rice farmers who currently do not use biopesticides, however, they are aware of commercial biopesticides products from various sources of information, such as various media platforms, fellow farmers, field demonstration, agricultural extension officers, educational programs, etc. Given this higher explanatory power, this study employs an extended UTAUT2 model to understand non-users' intention to use commercial biopesticides products among rice farmers in Indonesia. Thus, this study proposes that non-users' intention to use commercial biopesticide products is expected to be shaped by variables encompassing (1) performance expectancy, (2) effort expectancy, (3) social influence, (4) facilitating conditions, (5) price value, and (6) perceived need.

Figure 1: Original UTAUT2 framework

3. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

3.1. Performance expectancy

The performance expectancy variable is defined as “the degree to which using a technology will provide benefits to consumers in performing certain activities” (Venkatesh et al., 2012). Performance expectancy was found to be the strongest predictor of intention according to the study conducted by Venkatesh *et al.* (2003) and Venkatesh *et al.* (2012). Previous studies have repeatedly shown that performance expectancy variable had a positive and significant impact on intention (Aggarwal et al., 2019; Beza et al., 2018; Martín & Herrero, 2012; Plender et al., 2020). In the context of commercial biopesticides products, performance expectancy variable relates to non-users' perception of the advantages of these products in comparison to synthetic pesticides. If non-users perceive that using a commercial biopesticide product will lead to

improved pest and disease control, higher quality of crop yields, reduced environmental impact, or other desirable outcomes, they are likely to have positive performance expectancy. Positive performance expectancy contributes to a higher intention to use these products. Therefore, we hypothesize that performance expectancy has a positive and significant influence on non-users' intention to use commercial biopesticide products (H1).

3.2. Effort expectancy

Venkatesh et al. (2012) define the effort expectancy variable as “the degree of ease associated with consumers' use of the technology”. Previous studies carried out in a range of study contexts found that effort expectancy had a positive and significant impact on intention (Hayat et al., 2020; Sánchez-Torres et al., 2017).

If non-users perceive that using a commercial biopesticide product requires minimal effort, such as user-friendly, simple application processes, and clear instructions, they are more likely to have positive effort expectancy. Positive effort expectancy results to a higher intention to use this product. Accordingly, we hypothesize that effort expectancy has a positive and significant influence on non-users' intention to use commercial biopesticide products (H2).

3.3. Social influence

Venkatesh et al. (2012) defined that the social influence variable is “the extent to which consumers perceive that important others (e.g. family and friends) believe they should use a particular technology”. A positive and significant effect of social influence variable on intention was found in the previous studies by Aggarwal *et al* (2019), Slade *et al.* (2015), and Wu (2012). In the context of commercial biopesticides products, non-users' intention may be influenced by many actors, such as the experiences of their peers who have already benefitted from using commercial biopesticides products, educational programs from agricultural extension officers, and recommendations from sales agents of biopesticides industries.

Credible information or success stories from trusted individuals may enhance the social influence and, as a result it will affect the intention to utilize these products. Thus, we hypothesize that social influence has a positive and significant influence on non-users' intention to use commercial biopesticide products (H3).

3.4. Facilitating conditions

Facilitating conditions variable is defined as “consumers' perceptions of the resources and support available to perform a behavior” (Venkatesh et al., 2012). Previous studies found a positive and significant effect of facilitating conditions on intention (Buettner, 2017; Donaldson, 2011). Favorable facilitating conditions, such as product availability, technical support, and access to information and resources, may influence non-users' intention to use commercial biopesticide products. Hence, we hypothesize that facilitating conditions has a positive and significant influence on non-users' intention to use commercial biopesticide products (H4).

3.5. Price value

The price value variable is explained as “consumers’ cognitive tradeoff between the perceived benefits of the applications and the monetary cost of using them” (Venkatesh et al., 2012). According to Venkatesh et al. (2012), price value has a positive effect when the perceived benefits of using technology outweigh the associated costs. Several previous studies found a positive and significant impact of price value on intention (Plender et al., 2020; Schukat et al., 2019; Septiani et al., 2021). If non-users perceive that the potential benefits, such as improved pest control, safety for farmers’ health, reduced environmental impact, or increased quality of the crop yields, outweigh the price they have to pay, their perception of price value will be positive and this can result in a higher intention to use these products. Consequently, we hypothesize that price value has a positive and significant influence on non-users’ intention to use commercial biopesticide products (H5).

3.6. Perceived need

In the context of agricultural technology, Li *et al.* (2020) define the perceived need for technology characteristics as “the capabilities of the technologies to match the needs of farmers, which was influenced by the need characteristics and technology characteristics and had an impact on perceived benefits and intention to adopt”. The perceived need variable has been applied in previous studies that influence the intention and behavior (W. Li et al., 2020; Mukred et al., 2020). If non-users believe that commercial biopesticides products can meet their needs for example their needs for pest and disease control which can provide comparable or superior efficacy to synthetic pesticides, or farmers’ concern on pesticide resistance, pesticide residue, or market demands for residue-free products, therefore their perceived need will be positively aligned with these products. A greater perceived need can have an impact on a higher intention to use commercial biopesticides products. Therefore, we hypothesize that perceived need has a positive and significant influence on non-users’ intention to use commercial biopesticide products (H6).

Figure 2: The conceptual framework to examine non-users’ intention to use commercial biopesticide products by using an extended UTAUT2

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1. Sampling method

This study was carried out from December 2021 to March 2022 in one of the Indonesian rice-producing regions, namely Bogor Regency, West Java Province. Bogor Regency was purposively selected as the study site, due to the fact that 11 out of its 40 districts have the potential to develop organic and semi-organic rice farming (Wati et al., 2014). Data collection was carried out on rice farmers who met the criteria, namely farmers who currently do not use commercial biopesticide products in their pest and disease management practices, farmers who are aware of commercial biopesticide products from various sources of information, and farmers who are the decision-makers on the use of inputs for production for their farming business. There were 400 respondents of non-users, who were carefully selected by a purposive sampling technique.

A survey employing a structured questionnaire (Table 1) was used to gather data. The measurement items were adapted from several previous empirical studies. Each item was measured using a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 ('strongly disagree') to 5 ('strongly agree'). This study consists of 40 indicator variables and 7 latent variables.

Table 1: The questionnaire used for data collection

Latent variables dan indicator variables	Operational definition	References
<p>Performance expectancy (PE):</p> <p>PE1 – Commercial biopesticide products application can control pests and diseases effectively.</p> <p>PE2 – Commercial biopesticide products application will prevent from the occurrence of target pest resistance.</p> <p>PE3 - Commercial biopesticide products application will prevent from the declining in natural predators population.</p> <p>PE4 - Commercial biopesticide products application will prevent from environmental pollution.</p> <p>PE5 - Commercial biopesticide products application will be safer for fish.</p> <p>PE6 - Commercial biopesticide products application will be safer for the health of farmers.</p> <p>PE7 - Commercial biopesticide products application will result in better rice quality.</p> <p>PE8 - Commercial biopesticide products application will result in residue-free rice and safer for consumption.</p>	<p>The degree to which farmers are convinced that using commercial biopesticide products will be beneficial.</p>	<p>(Akyüz & Theuvsen, 2020; Ataei et al., 2021; Rezaei et al., 2020; Sharifzadeh et al., 2017; Venkatesh et al., 2012)</p>
<p>Effort expectancy (EE):</p> <p>EE1 - How to use commercial biopesticide products is something that I can pick up quickly.</p> <p>EE2 – It is clear and easy to understand how to use commercial biopesticide products.</p> <p>EE3 – I believe that commercial biopesticide products are easy to be applied.</p> <p>EE4 – I believe that it is easy to become skilled in using commercial biopesticide products.</p>	<p>The extent to which farmers perceive that commercial biopesticide products are user-friendly.</p>	<p>(Faridi et al., 2020; Rezaei et al., 2020; Venkatesh et al., 2012)</p>

Latent variables dan indicator variables	Operational definition	References
<p>Social influence (SI): SI1 - My family encourage me to utilize commercial biopesticide products. SI2 - Other farmers encourage me to utilize commercial biopesticide products. SI3 - The farmer group leader encourage me to utilize commercial biopesticide products. SI4 - The agricultural extension officers persuade me to utilize commercial biopesticide products. SI5 - Sales staff from biopesticides companies persuade me to utilize commercial biopesticide products. SI6 - The agriculture kiosks persuade me to utilize commercial biopesticide products.</p>	<p>The degree to which farmers believe that other significant individuals share their opinion that farmers should utilize commercial biopesticide products.</p>	<p>(Rasyidha et al., 2020; Schukat et al., 2019; Venkatesh et al., 2012)</p>
<p>Facilitating Condition (FC): FC1 - I have the costs required to apply commercial biopesticide products. FC2 - I have the manpower required to apply commercial biopesticide products. FC3 - I have the information required to apply commercial biopesticide products. FC4 - I think it is easy to consult with agricultural extension officers. FC5 - I think it is easy to consult with private extension officers from biopesticide companies. FC6 - I can attend a training on biopesticides. FC7 - Commercial biopesticide products can be purchased at farmers' kiosks. FC8 - Commercial biopesticide products can be purchased at online stores.</p>	<p>Farmers' opinions about the support and resources available for using commercial biopesticide products.</p>	<p>(Faridi et al., 2020; Sharifzadeh et al., 2017; Venkatesh et al., 2012)</p>
<p>Price value (PV): PV1 - Commercial biopesticide products have reasonable prices. PV2 - Using commercial biopesticide products is more advantageous than the costs.</p>	<p>Perceptions of the advantages from using commercial biopesticide products in relation to the expenses associated with their application.</p>	<p>(Venkatesh et al., 2012)</p>
<p>Perceived need (PN): PN1 - The usage of synthetic pesticides does not satisfy me. PN2 - Commercial biopesticide products can be used to meet my needs. PN3 - I would like to utilize commercial biopesticide products. PN4 - I require a commercial biopesticide product that is more environmentally friendly. PN5 - I require a commercial biopesticides product to produce rice without any residue. PN6 - After knowing the advertisement of commercial biopesticide products, I felt compelled to utilize them. PN7 - After learning about biopesticide from extension activities, I felt compelled to utilize commercial biopesticide products.</p>	<p>The degree to which farmers believe that they need commercial biopesticide products to support their farming.</p>	<p>(Jeong et al., 2009; Kang & Moneyham, 2010; Lin et al., 2015; Warshaw, 1980; Zhu & He, 2002)</p>

Latent variables dan indicator variables	Operational definition	References
PN8 – After learning about biopesticide from fellow farmers, I felt compelled to utilize commercial biopesticide products.		
Intention (INT) : INT1 - I will find out where to buy commercial biopesticide products. INT2 - I will save money to purchase commercial biopesticide products. INT3 - I am planning to use a commercial biopesticide product over the next growing season. INT4 - I am planning to purchase a commercial biopesticide product over the next growing season.	The efforts made by farmers to use commercial biopesticide products.	(Abadi, 2018; Rezaei et al., 2019; Venkatesh et al., 2012)

4.2. Method of data analysis

This study employed statistical analysis techniques using structural equation modeling (SEM). The collected data were processed using Lineal Structural Relationship (LISREL) software version 8.72.

5. RESULTS

5.1. Respondent characteristics

A significant proportion of respondents fell within the age bracket of 35 to 64 years old (76.3%). In contrast, a relatively small percentage were younger than 35 years old (10.5%) and older than 65 years old (13.3%). The vast majority were literate (95.8%), dominated by farmers who had attended elementary school (72%). Most of the respondents were male (74.5%), and only 25.5% were female. In terms of farming experience, most farmers have more than 10 years of experience (78.5%), while the rest have only been farming for less than 10 years (21.5%). More than half of the respondents owned paddy fields < 0.5 hectares (59%), with 24.3% owned land ranging from 0.5 to 0.99 hectares, while the remaining 16.8% owned one hectare or more. This finding is in line with the report on rice farmers' characteristics in Indonesia. Paddy field ownership by farmers in Indonesia is relatively small, and is dominated by farmers who only own an area of <0.5 ha (76%) (BPS, 2018). The high number of smallholders in Indonesia is generally caused by land conversion (Ruswandi et al., 2007) and land fragmentation due to inheritance (Darwis, 2008).

Table 2: Profile of the respondent

Profile	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
1. Age (years old)		
- < 35	42	10.5
- 35-44	82	20.5
- 45-54	120	30.0
- 55-64	103	25.8
- ≥ 65	53	13.3
2. Formal education		
- Never attending school	17	4.4

Profile	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
- Not completed elementary school	44	11.0
- Elementary school	244	61.0
- Junior high school	49	12.3
- Senior high school	37	9.3
- Diploma degree	2	0.5
- Bachelor degree	7	1.8
3. Gender		
- Male	298	74.5
- Female	102	25.5
4. Farming experience (year)		
- < 10	86	21.5
- 10-19	88	22.0
- 20-29	96	24.0
- \geq 30	130	32.5
5. Size of farm land (hectare)		
- < 0,5	236	59.0
- 0,5 – 0,99	97	24.3
- 1 – 1,99	50	12.5
- \geq 2	17	4.3

5.2. The results of the measurement model testing

The survey revealed three indicator variables - SI5, FC5, and PN6 - all with the same response (scale 1). This uniformity resulted from the absence of any promotion of commercial biopesticide products by a particular company in the research sites. Consequently, these three indicators were omitted from the data analysis.

The validity of the indicator variables that make up a construct can be assessed through the standardized factor loading (SFL) values. In addition to the SFL value, the p-value also needs to be considered in determining whether an indicator variable is statistically significant and has a systematic relationship with its latent variable. In this study, the criteria used to test the indicators are considered valid if they have standardized factor loadings > 0.7 and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) > 0.5 , while constructs are considered reliable if they have a value of Composite Reliability (CR) > 0.7 and Cronbach's Alpha (CA) > 0.7 (Hair et al., 2014).

The results of the confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) revealed that some indicator variables had standardized factor loading (SFL) values below 0.7. Consequently, these variables were excluded from the measurement model, and a retest of the model was conducted. Subsequently, it was found that 18 indicator variables had SFL values > 0.7 , indicating that all indicator variables met the criteria for convergent validity. Despite two indicators, PE6 and FC8, having SFL values below 0.70, they were still retained in the analysis due to the satisfactory validity and reliability values of the corresponding latent variables. Hence, the inclusion of these indicator variables was believed appropriate.

In addition, in terms of construct validity, the AVE values of each latent variable exceeded 0.5 (> 0.5), implying that all the latent variables used were valid. The values of CA and CR for each latent variable were above 0.70 (> 0.70) demonstrating that all the latent variables

employed in this model are reliable. Among the eight indicators used to evaluate the goodness of fit of the structural model, all indicators met the criteria except for the Chi-square p-value criterion (not fit). Hence, it can be inferred that the structural model demonstrated a favorable alignment with the dataset.

Table 3: Results of validity test and reliability test

Latent Variables and Indicator Variables	SFL	P-value	AVE	Results	Cronbach's Alpha (CA)	Composite Reliability (CR)	Results
Performance Expectancy			0.50	Valid	0.74	0.75	Reliable
PE6	0.64	0.00		Valid			
PE7	0.72	0.00		Valid			
PE8	0.76	0.00		Valid			
Effort Expectancy			0.73	Valid	0.92	0.92	Reliable
EE1	0.87	0.00		Valid			
EE2	0.81	0.00		Valid			
EE3	0.90	0.00		Valid			
EE4	0.84	0.00		Valid			
Social Influence			0.82	Valid	0.89	0.90	Reliable
SI2	0.90	0.00		Valid			
SI3	0.91	0.00		Valid			
Facilitating Condition			0.51	Valid	0.75	0.76	Reliable
FC1	0.75	0.00		Valid			
FC2	0.71	0.00		Valid			
FC8	0.68	0.00		Valid			
Price Value			0.74	Valid	0.83	0.85	Reliable
PV1	0.79	0.00		Valid			
PV2	0.93	0.00		Valid			
Perceived Need			0.77	Valid	0.92	0.93	Reliable
PN2	0.79	0.00		Valid			
PN3	0.88	0.00		Valid			
PN4	0.92	0.00		Valid			
PN5	0.90	0.00		Valid			
Intention			0.50	Valid	0.75	0.75	Reliable
INT1	0.71	0.00		Valid			
INT2	0.70	0.00		Valid			
INT4	0.71	0.00		Valid			

Table 4: Goodness of Fit Model

Goodness of Fit	Values	Cut off	Results
Degrees of Freedom	168	> 0.00	Fit
Chi-square p-value	0.00	> 0.05	Not Fit
RMSEA	0.07	< 0.08	Fit
GFI	0.90	> 0.90	Fit
CFI	0.96	> 0.95	Fit
NFI	0.94	> 0.90	Fit
IFI	0.96	> 0.90	Fit
SRMR	0.05	< 0.05	Fit

Moreover, R2 for the non-users' intention to use commercial biopesticide products among rice farmers was 75%. This implied that the components of the extended UTAUT2 could explain a 75% variance of the intention.

5.3. Hypotheses testing

As per the findings from hypothesis testing, it is evident that 5 out of 6 latent variables had a statistically significant impact on the intention to utilize commercial biopesticide products. To be specific, hypotheses H2, H3, H4, H5, and H6 were supported, whereas H1 was not supported (refer to Table 5). Farmers were shown to be more likely to use commercial biopesticide products when they had a more positive perception of effort expectancy, stronger social influence, better presence of facilitating conditions, higher price value, and greater perceived need. Nonetheless, it was shown that there was no correlation between behavioral intention and performance expectancy. This finding contradicts with that of the study by Venkatesh et al. (2012).

Table 5: The results of hypotheses testing

Hypotheses	Path	Path Coefficient	p-values	Results
H1	PE → INT	0.02	0.34	H1: Not Supported
H2	EE → INT	0.15	0.00	H2: Supported
H3	SI → INT	0.14	0.00	H3: Supported
H4	FC → INT	0.16	0.00	H4: Supported
H5	PV → INT	0.17	0.00	H5: Supported
H6	PN → INT	0.65	0.00	H6 : Supported

Figure 3: The estimated SEM path model

6. DISCUSSION

Our study did not yield the expected result, as there was no significant association found between performance expectancy and the intention of non-users to use commercial biopesticide products. This result is in line with previous studies conducted by Septiani et al. (2021) and Fox et al. (2018). In the context of commercial biopesticides products, this suggests that non-users may perceive that performance expectancy is insignificant to their intention to utilize biopesticides because they have been relying on synthetic pesticides for their pest and disease management practices. Over time, they have observed the effectiveness of synthetic pesticides and have achieved satisfactory results in terms of pest and disease control as well as the crop yields. As a result, they may not see a strong reason to switch to biopesticides. Their prior experience with synthetic pesticides and the positive outcomes they have obtained from using them can shape their perception of performance expectancy. They may believe that synthetic pesticides already provide the desired results, making them less inclined to consider alternative solutions such as biopesticides. Moreover, non-users may have limited knowledge or

awareness about the potential benefits and advantages of biopesticides compared to synthetic pesticides. They may perceive biopesticides as less effective or unproven in their ability to deliver the same level of performance as synthetic pesticides. This perception further diminishes the perceived significance of performance expectancy in their intention to use biopesticides. Overall, the satisfaction derived from the use of synthetic pesticides, combined with limited awareness and skepticism about biopesticides, contributes to the perception that performance expectancy is not a major consideration in intention to utilize commercial biopesticides products. The lack of a substantial correlation between performance expectancy and intention to utilize biopesticides underscores the importance of targeted educational and awareness programs aimed at enhancing non-users' understanding of the potential benefits and advantages associated with using biopesticides. By addressing their concerns and providing them with accurate information, it may be possible to increase their intention to use biopesticides in their farming practices.

The relevance of effort expectancy in the context of commercial biopesticide products was further demonstrated by the fact that it was a substantial positive predictor of behavioral intention. This result aligns with earlier research that has consistently emphasized the relationship between effort expectancy and non-users' intention (Hilal & Varela-Neira, 2022; Li et al., 2022). When non-users perceive that adopting and using commercial biopesticide products requires minimal effort, such as user-friendly, clear instructions, and minimal training, they are more likely to have positive effort expectancy. Positive effort expectancy would, in turn, contribute to a higher intention to utilize these products. To promote the intention to utilize commercial biopesticide products among non-users, it would be beneficial for the industry to address and mitigate any perceived barriers related to effort expectancy. This could involve improving product usability, providing clear and user-friendly instructions, offering training programs, and highlighting the potential benefits and advantages of using biopesticides over synthetic pesticides.

Furthermore, social influence has a considerable influence on intention of non-users to utilize commercial biopesticide products. This finding aligns with previous research that have consistently found social influence as an important factor driving technology acceptance among non-users across various contexts (Hilal & Varela-Neira, 2022; Maduku, 2016; Saprikis et al., 2022). To address the reluctance of non-users to use commercial biopesticide products, producers may need to identify key influencers within their target market and leverage their influence to actively promote the use of these products among non-users.

This study found that the effect of facilitating conditions on non-users' behavioural intention to utilize commercial biopesticide products is significant. This result aligns with the conclusion of previous studies, which have consistently found a substantial association between these two variables (Gunasinghe & Nanayakkara, 2021; Hilal & Varela-Neira, 2022; Lau et al., 2020; Maduku, 2016). When non-users believe that resources and other support systems are insufficient, they are less likely to start utilizing commercial biopesticide products. Therefore, implementing strategies that provide adequate support systems to facilitate the use of commercial biopesticide products, along with regular communication about the accessibility

of these support systems to the target market, becomes crucial for biopesticide producers to overcome non-users' resistance and encourage the use of this technology.

The fact that there is a correlation between price value and intention of non-users and a positive link between them supports hypothesis 5, which indicating that price value affects intention to utilize commercial biopesticides. This finding is in line with previous study by Septiani et al. (2021). Non-users assess the value concerning the price of commercial biopesticide products, considering potential benefits (such as improved pest and disease control, reduced environmental impact, safety for human health, increased quality of crop yields, and enhanced marketability that can generate economic benefits). Positive price value increases the likelihood to use the commercial biopesticide products. To promote the non-users' intention to use, biopesticide producers can provide information on economic benefits and present cost-benefit analyses, which can help non-users make informed decisions and positively influence their perception of price value.

A positive relationship was found between perceived need and non-users' intention to use commercial biopesticides, which aligns with a previous study on the intention to utilize 3G services (Lin et al., 2015). Non-users' perceived needs can influence their intention to use commercial biopesticides when they believe that biopesticides can meet their pest and disease control needs, reduce environmental harm, and provide comparable efficacy to synthetic pesticides. To promote the intention to use among non-users, education and awareness programs are important, providing accurate information, workshops, demonstrations, or sharing success stories, can help non-users understand the efficacy of biopesticides and inspire them. In addition, highlighting comparative advantages, such as compatibility with integrated pest management and suitability for organic farming, can address specific needs and promote intention to use as a result.

Furthermore, the integration of perceived need into the UTAUT2 model significantly improves its predictive power by 75%, surpassing the original UTAUT2 model's predictive power of 74% (Venkatesh et al., 2012). This result corroborates the important role of the perceived need aspect within the context of commercial biopesticide product use.

7. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study revealed that effort expectancy, social influence, facilitating conditions, price value, and perceived need had positive impacts on the intention of non-users to utilize commercial biopesticide products. However, the impact of performance expectancy was statistically insignificant, which contradicts the theoretical model of UTAUT2. This can be attributed to non-users' perception that they have been using synthetic pesticides for a long time and are satisfied with their performance, resulting in a lack of perceived benefits of commercial biopesticides products.

This study contributes to the extended of the UTAUT2 framework by introducing an additional construct that is valuable in predicting the acceptance behavior of non-users, specifically in the scope of the intention to utilize commercial biopesticide products among rice farmers.

Considering the perceived needs of farmers proves to be valuable in understanding and predicting the intentions of non-users to use biopesticides. The decision to use a particular technology is contingent on its compatibility with the farmers' goals. Similarly, the decision-making process of farmers regarding the use of commercial biopesticide products can be influenced by the extent to which they perceive a need for biopesticides. Therefore, to comprehend farmers' decision-making process in using commercial biopesticides products, it is important to assess whether the use of biopesticides aligns with the needs of farmers.

Declaration of interests statement

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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